
SELECTED DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS AND FAMILY RELATIONS AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

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Abstract

The study investigated into the relations between selected demographic factors and their influence on family relations of higher secondary students in the Indian context. Descriptive survey design has been implemented for the study and simple random sampling technique were used to a sample participant of 1300 higher secondary students of Kanchipuram district, Tamil Nadu, India. Index of family relations scale and information blank to understand their demographic background has been used to collect data. One-way ANOVA, t-test and mean were used to analyse the data. Research findings reported that type of school management, parent qualification, gender, and location of home of the higher secondary students influence family relations. The study concludes with recommendations for further research on demographic factors and family relations, and individual development in terms of important theoretical and methodological issues yet to be addressed ([Rand D. Conger et al., 2010](#)). Therefore both school systems and parent guidance programs are crucial for helping students develop positive understanding of family.

keywords: family relations, adolescents, type of school management, gender.

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Introduction

Stress and strain are part of every human life. Adolescence is a stage where the individual starts experiencing both positive and negative emotions from life more consistently. This is a stage where the relationships get evolved and shaped. Proper adjustment and management of self and with society is crucial during this developmental stage of life characterised by profound psychological change (Lerner et al., 1996). Family being a social unit, the adolescent tries to fit in to the roles and responsibilities at this stage. This is crucial as because of growth and maturation. Adolescent undergoes physical, emotional, social transformation from inside out. It is also a stage where they work hard to shape his career. Proper adjustment with school life will enable developing positive outlook on personal life of adolescent child. Students' choice of school is also reflective of the family status. Despite the importance of adolescent transition and the family relations in developmental psychology, there have unfortunately, been few published studies that have investigated how and why the family relations changes during adolescence. Much of our

understanding of changes in family relations during higher secondary level is, consequently, based on generalisations from cross-sectional studies which have led several reviewers to identify the importance of selected demographic factors and its influence on family relations at the higher secondary level. Therefore the present investigation examines family relations of adolescents studying in government, government-aided and private schools. In the present study, we sought to add to the growing longitudinal database on the family relations by investigating the changes in adolescents' perception of their relationships within the family at the higher secondary stage (Matt McGue., et al., (2006). This paper will present how family relations among higher secondary adolescents of Kanchipuram are influenced by type of school management, and gender.

FAMILY RELATIONS (FR)

Family is a single unit of people who live together and share life's basic day-by-day functions. During adolescence these dual, sometimes contrasting, human needs create the paradoxes of the family unit, in which exists struggle for separateness and togetherness, differentness and sameness, protection and freedom, support and independence (Dodson L.S. & Kurpius, D. J. 1977). Higher secondary students relationship with parents is restructured even while stable features of the relationship established in childhood endure (Collins & Repinski, 1994). As family being the place where emotions are strong and cohesive, at times these emotional bonds create lot of challenges when the adjustment of the adolescent within the family gets strained. Moreover increased expression of negative affect (Buchanan, Eccles, & Becker, 1992) and dis-inhibited behaviour (Moffitt, 1993) are further likely to strain the relationships of adolescents within the family, resulting in greater conflict and emotional disturbance (Steinberg, 1987, 1990) and hence strains family relations. Therefore let us discuss about certain demographic factors which perhaps their influences on family relations during higher secondary students.

Type of School

Any researcher will feel family relations and type of school are not related. But, if one can probe little deep, we can find family support and understanding will culturally translate into support for academics. This awareness in the family will generally translate into a school which is not only affordable but also considered good for the child. So when family understanding is positive parents concern towards their ward education are generally higher and hence, choose a school which they feel is better, affordable and possible.

Course Specialization

Family is a social unit, parents involvement in higher secondary school going children's selection of course vary from individual family economy and culture. If parents are educated, their influence on course selection at the higher secondary level generally higher than parents who are not educated. In government schools course selection is purely governed by marks and teachers guidance while in matriculation schools, parents' desire for better education generally focuses on science or commerce stream for their wards. But in general family relations are course specialization are not directly related.

Parents Qualification

Parents who are educated are believed to maintain positive family relations. They show more understanding and respect for their family members. In Tamil Nadu, parents who are qualified and have a decent job mostly work hard for the growth of the family. Though this doesn't mean that less qualified or uneducated have poor family relations.

Gender

Do daughters and sons have different sort of relationships with their mothers and parents? A tentative answer to this question is a surprising one. In general, differences between the family relations of sons and daughters are minimal (Silverberg and Jacob, 1992). Although there are occasional exceptions to the rules, sons and daughters report similar degree of closeness to their parents, similar amount of conflict, similar types of rules (and disagreements about those rules), and similar patterns of activity (Hill and Holmbeck 1987). These same studies also indicate that adolescents tend to be closer to their mother, to spend more time alone with their mother, and to feel more comfortable talking about problems and other emotional matters. But some researches reflect the opposite view. From early to mid-adolescence (ages 11-14), youth reported conflict with parents increased and warmth decreased, especially for girls, compared to boys (McGue, Elkins, Walden & Lacono, 2005). These increases in conflict and decreases in warmth are thought to occur primarily between middle childhood and adolescence. Studies investigating developmental change in parent-child relationship quality have shown that parent-child conflict increases and parent-child warmth / closeness decreases. Another dimension to this is Fathers are perceived as relatively distant authority figures who may be consulted for "objective" information (such as help with homework). Interestingly, adolescents fight more often with their mothers, this higher level of conflict does not appear to jeopardize the closeness of the mother-adolescent relationship.

Location of Home

It is common belief that family life in urban area is hectic, and interaction among member of the family is relatively meagre. While comparing with members of rural family, life is relatively slow, steady and mostly joint family type and extended family members also live in the vicinity of their house. Greater socialization is evident in rural setup while families living in urban area experience relatively lesser interaction between family members. This doesn't evidently reflect on family relations. Family relations are how members of family interact and react to their everyday life event especially here in the context of adolescence. Some researchers suggest that educated parents develop proper channels of communication with their adolescent child and so better relations while few others believe that rural family setup is more diverse to take care of adolescents and their family relations. But arguably in this research, both urban and rural population have nuclear family and hence mostly educated urban family members might slightly edged over rural family in terms of their relations with their adolescent child. This is precisely is the line of argument of this research and we need to see how it is reflected in this particular research findings.

Family Income

The family climate created by economic strain puts adolescents at risk for a wide variety of problems. Economic well being, gives a sense of adequacy to a child. Studies conducted to explore the influence of economic factors on the kind of relationship existing in the family prove that low income (Angell, 1936), unemployment, uneducated/less, well educated parent, single parent have adverse impact on the relationship between the family members and between the adolescence and their parents. Adolescents belonging to such families appear to be more quarrelsome with each other and have adjustment problems both at home and at school. They also exhibit poor academic achievement.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to determine the influence of selected demographic factors on family relations among higher secondary students of Kanchipuram district of Tamil Nadu, India.

Research Questions

The research questions that guided the study were:

Whether type of school management, course specialization, parents qualification, gender, location of home, family income had influence on family relations?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Descriptive survey design is used in the study in which the population of interest is identified and were surveyed. According to Key, 1997, it is the information describing what exists in a given condition and situation.

Population and Sampling Procedure

The study population was higher secondary students from government, government-aided and private matriculation school students of Kanchipuram district, India. Lottery type of simple random sampling method was used as this created equal opportunity for every school to be selected.

Instrumentation

Index of family relations scale by Walter Hudson with 30 statements was used for the study. Likert scale type response ranged from “strongly agree” to “strongly disagree.” To elicit demographic background of the sample population, information blank was provided along with the scale.

Data Collection

Copies of the index of family relations along with Performa were personally administered to the sample in their schools. Before administering the scale, participants were explained about the purpose and significance of the study. In this way investigator ensured credibility of the response. Sufficient time was given to every respondent before taking back the filled in scale.

Data Analysis Plan

Statistical techniques like t-test and F test using SPSS 16 was carried out to statistically interpret the data collected. Calculating mean value was useful to compare means between two groups and

interpret accordingly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

H₀₁: Type of school management has no significant influence on family relations.

Table 1 – One-way ANOVA for Family Relations and Type of School

Category		N	Mean	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Inference
Type of School	government	752	3.3582	Between Groups	10.284	2	5.142	24.139*	*Significant
	aided	236	3.1233	Within Groups	276.283	1297	.213		
	private	312	3.2627	Total	286.567	1299			

*p<0.05

From the above table 1, it can be inferred that F-value of family relations is 24.139, which is statistically significant at 0.05 level with df=2/1297. This indicates that the mean scores of family relations with respect to government, government-aided and private higher secondary school students differ remarkably. Hence, the Null hypothesis (H₀₁) stating no significant difference in family relations with respect to type of school management is “not accepted.” Further, on comparing the mean scores it is found that students from government school (M=3.3582) have superior mean value compared with private (M=3.2627) and government-aided schools (M=3.1233).

Generally it is assumed in Indian sub-continent that family relations among private school students’ are better. But this is not true all the time. Recent trends show lot of discomforts experienced by adolescence from middle and higher class families compared to poor children. This could be accounted to economically poor children and exposed to harsh realities of life from a young age and hence adapt well during adolescence. Moreover, there government school students parents relatively exhibit less pressure on their wards to perform well academically.

Course Specialization

H₀₂: Course specialization has no significant influence on family relations.

Table 2 – One-way ANOVA for Family Relations and Course Specialization

Category		N	Mean	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Inference
Course Specialization	science	569	3.3034	Between Groups	.719	2	.360	1.632	Not Significant
	arts	464	3.3060	Within Groups	285.848	1297	.220		
	vocational	267	3.2464	Total	286.567	1299			

The F value from table 2 shows there is no compelling difference between family relations based on course of specialization among higher secondary school students of Kanchipuram district. This indicates that the mean scores of family relations of students studying in science, arts and vocational stream did not differ significantly. Hence the null hypothesis (H₀₂) is not rejected. It may be inferred that higher secondary students from different streams (science, arts & Vocational) were found to have same degree of family relations.

Parents Qualification

H₀₃: Parents qualification has no significant influence on family relations.

Table 3 - One-way ANOVA for Family Relations and Parent's Qualification

Category		N	Mean	Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Inference
Parent Qualification	illiterate	146	3.3010	Between Groups	4.060	2	2.030	9.320*	*Significant
	upto XII Std	456	3.2183	Within Groups	282.507	1297	.218		
	graduation and above	698	3.3395	Total	286.567	1299			

From table 3, it is evident that F-value is 9.320 which is statistically significant at 0.05 level with df= 2/1297. This shows that there is a compelling difference in mean scores of family relations among higher secondary school students of different parental qualification. Therefore the null hypothesis (H₀₃) of no statistical significant difference in family relations with respect to parent qualification is not accepted thereby rejecting null hypothesis. This infers that Parent Qualification has a significant influence on family relations at the higher secondary level. The family relations mean value for students whose parents are graduate and above is slightly higher when compared with students from parents whose qualification is up to XII or even less. This can be attributed to the fact that graduate parents are aware about adolescent issues and show higher levels of flexibility when dealing with adolescent children. Additionally parents qualification perhaps translated into positive family culture and to a certain extent higher social status because of employment demonstrates stability in family (Duncan & Magnuson, 2003). These factors could have possibly reflected in their level of family relations. But the table also infer that students from illiterate parents exhibit greater levels of satisfaction in their family relations. This also shows that parents' education is not a major factor all the time but family ideals and rich values embedded in ones culture can be a pressing factor for perceived positive family relations by higher secondary students of Kanchipuram district.

Gender

H₀₄: Gender has no significant influence on family relations.

Table 4 – Independent Sample t-test for family relations and Gender

Category		N	Mean	df	t-value	Inference
Gender	Male	811	3.4275	1298	14.342*	Significant
	female	489	3.0690			

*Significant at 5% level

It is evident from the table 4 that t-value of family relations is 14.342 which is significant at 0.05 level with df=1298. This shows that mean value of family relations differ measurably. On comparing the means, boys outperform girls in family relations score. Culturally, Kanchipuram is temple town with people imbibing more traditional values; masculinity is quite common in home culture. Men possess more power and women's role is mostly home maker. Recently with industrialization, gender neutrality value gained momentum in the social setup. Dimensions of social position, including prestige, power, and economic well-being (Hoff, Laursen, & Tardiff, 2002; Oakes & Rossi, 2003) are being challenged in Indian homes. In this context there is a clash in values with the new generation of youngsters especially girls challenging traditional beliefs and practices. This silent conflict has been reflected in this analysis with boys feel and receives more support from the mothers of conservative culture of Kanchipuram not to forget girls gaining more support from educated parents and especially fathers. But still Kanchipuram being a temple town with traditions strongly embedded in family life style, higher secondary boys are better placed in family and consequently family relations when compared with girls is measurably on the higher side.

Location of Home

H₀₅: Location of home has no significant influence on family relations.

Table 5 – Independent Sample t-test for family relations and Location of Home

Category		N	Mean	df	t-value	Inference
Location of Home	rural	512	3.2456	1298	2.920*	Significant
	urban	788	3.3232			

*p<0.05.

The t-value of family relations is (2.920) which is statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance and df=1298. The mean scores of family relations of rural and urban students are notably different in statistical terms. So there is a significant influence of location of home on family relations. Thus the null hypothesis (H₀₅) that there is no significant influence of location of home on family relations is not accepted.

The mean value shows that students coming from urban background (M=3.2456) have better family relations when compared to students coming from rural background (M=3.3232). The reason can be attributed to urban family have relatively better facilities additionally Parents are

often seen exhibiting greater affection, love, care and concern for their wards which is not so among students coming from rural homes ([Rand D. Conger](#)). Moreover social positions are positively correlated (Ensminger & Fothergill, 2003) and this could have contributed to the difference in family relations between rural and urban higher secondary students.

Family Income

H₀₆: Family income has no significant influence on family relations.

Table 6 – Independent Sample t-test for family relations and Family income

Category		N	Mean	df	t-value	Inference
family Income	less than 25000	519	3.2869	1298	.360	Not Significant
	greater than 25000	781	3.2965			

Inference

It is inferred from table 6 that the t-value for family income is not statistically significant. It shows that the mean scores of family relations with respect to less than Rs.25,000/- income and greater than Rs.25,000/- income do not differ largely. So there is no remarkable influence of family income on family relations of higher secondary school students. Hence the null hypothesis (h₀₆) stating there is no influence on family income on family relations is not rejected. In other words, students from family income less than Rs.25,000/- and more than Rs.25,000/- have same degree of family relations. But research shows socio-economic status captures various dimensions of social positions, including prestige, power, and economic well-being (Hoff, Laursen, & Tardiff, 2002). Moreover occupation and income are significant influencers (Krieger, Williams & Moss, 1997) which is not captured in this study.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

From the results of the study, it could be concluded that family relations is influenced by type of school, parents qualification, gender, location of home among higher secondary students of Kanchipuram district. Course specialization and family income were not influencing family relations of higher secondary students of Kanchipuram district. It can be concluded that family relations during transition stage of adolescence is a complex phenomena. A clear generalisation is a challenge as many factors influence family relations. To summarize family relations is significantly influenced by four demographic factors. Further research is crucial for gaining additional understanding of how type of school management, parents' qualification, gender, and location of home conveys developmental advantage across higher secondary students' relation with the family. Given this progress in-depth analysis especially in the Indian context is very important to clearly gain insights and research priorities that will enhance knowledge for further accurate and meaningful generalizations in the coming years.

COMMENTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The study on demographic factors on family relations among higher secondary students has advanced both theoretically and empirically during the past several years. Theoretical developments have advanced beyond earlier assumptions about family relations and has stressed on multiple reasons clearly emphasising widening of knowledge in a given context to identify possible reasons. In this regard, the following recommendations and further research are suggested below:

1. Higher secondary students' relations within the family needs to be strengthened and longitudinal study have to be carried out in the Indian context.
2. Improved facilities and learning ambiance in school at the higher secondary level will indirectly address academic cum family relations issues at home.
3. Guidance and counseling services should be strengthened in school for higher secondary students.
4. Strengthening of Parent-teachers association will reduce the gap between school, parent and students in the process enable academic transactions and family relations at home.
5. Longitudinal study in terms of family process, socio-economic status, adolescents' individual differences have to be studies.
6. Introduction of genetic information into the study on family relations will give more comprehension and idea about demographic influence on family relations.
7. New research looking beyond the family to target possible mediators involving peers, school and community characteristics which may enhance the explanatory power of demographic factors influence on family relations and hence need to be studied.

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